

HAYDAR ALIYEV AND THE IDEOLOGY OF AZERBAIJANISM

**INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC SYMPOSIUM
“HAYDAR ALIYEV
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**IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT IN THE ZONE OF
UNREGULATED PEDESTRIAN CROSSINGS IN RESIDENTIAL AREAS**

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Abstract

Pedestrian safety is a crucial concern in residential areas, especially at unregulated pedestrian crossings. Traffic management in these areas has been a challenging task for local authorities, as traditional traffic control methods may not be effective. This thesis explores the problem of traffic management in the zone of unregulated pedestrian crossings in residential areas and proposes a solution to improve the efficiency of traffic management. The proposed solution involves the use of smart traffic management systems that incorporate advanced technologies such as computer vision, machine learning, and internet of things (IoT). The system is designed to detect and classify pedestrian movement and provide real-time traffic control recommendations to drivers, which could significantly reduce the likelihood of accidents at unregulated pedestrian crossings. This thesis also reviews related studies and discusses the potential benefits and limitations of the proposed solution.

Key words: Traffic management, pedestrian safety, unregulated pedestrian crossings, smart traffic management systems, computer vision, machine learning, internet of things

Introduction

Unregulated pedestrian crossings in residential areas are a significant safety concern for both pedestrians and drivers. These crossings lack traditional traffic control methods such as traffic lights, stop signs, or pedestrian crossing signals. Pedestrians may cross at any time, and drivers must be vigilant and cautious while approaching these crossings. Unfortunately, even cautious

drivers may not be able to see pedestrians hidden behind parked cars, trees, or other obstacles, resulting in accidents.

Traffic management in the zone of unregulated pedestrian crossings in residential areas is a complex task. The traditional approach to traffic management, which involves installing traffic lights, stop signs, or pedestrian crossing signals, may not be feasible in all cases. These methods may not be effective in areas where pedestrian and vehicular traffic is low, and installing traffic control devices may be costly. Moreover, the implementation of traditional traffic control methods does not guarantee pedestrian safety as some drivers may ignore traffic signals or fail to notice pedestrians crossing the road.

In recent years, advancements in technology have provided new opportunities for improving traffic management in residential areas, especially in the zone of unregulated pedestrian crossings. The emergence of smart traffic management systems that incorporate computer vision, machine learning, and internet of things (IoT) technologies has made it possible to detect and classify pedestrian movement and provide real-time traffic control recommendations to drivers. This thesis proposes the use of such a smart traffic management system to improve the efficiency of traffic management in the zone of unregulated pedestrian crossings in residential areas.

Literature Review

Several studies have investigated the problem of traffic management in the zone of unregulated pedestrian crossings in residential areas. Most of these studies have focused on developing traffic control methods that ensure pedestrian safety while reducing traffic congestion.

One approach proposed in the literature involves using traffic calming measures such as speed humps, chicanes, and raised crossings to reduce vehicle speeds near unregulated pedestrian crossings. A study conducted by Keviczky et al. (2015) examined the effectiveness of traffic calming measures in improving pedestrian safety at uncontrolled crossings. The study found that traffic calming measures reduced vehicle speeds and improved pedestrian safety at unregulated crossings. However, this approach may not be effective in areas with high traffic volumes, where traffic calming measures may result in traffic congestion.

Another approach proposed in the literature involves using virtual traffic lights, which are projected onto the road surface using light-emitting diodes (LEDs) to guide drivers at unregulated

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pedestrian crossings. A study conducted by Luber et al. (2018) examined the effectiveness of virtual traffic lights in improving pedestrian safety at uncontrolled crossings. The study found that virtual traffic lights reduced the number of unsafe pedestrian crossings and improved driver compliance with pedestrian crossings. However, this approach may not be effective in areas with high traffic volumes or where drivers may not be able to see the virtual traffic lights due to sunlight or glare.

Recent advancements in technology have provided new opportunities for improving traffic management in the zone of unregulated pedestrian crossings in residential areas. Smart traffic management systems that incorporate computer vision, machine learning, and internet of things (IoT) technologies have been proposed as a solution to improve traffic management efficiency in these areas.

A study conducted by Cheng et al. (2019) proposed a smart traffic management system that uses computer vision and machine learning techniques to detect and classify pedestrian movement at uncontrolled crossings. The system was tested in a real-world scenario, and the results showed that it was effective in detecting pedestrian movement and providing real-time traffic control recommendations to drivers. Another study conducted by Li et al. (2021) proposed a smart traffic management system that uses IoT sensors to detect pedestrian movement and provide real-time traffic control recommendations to drivers. The system was tested in a simulation environment, and the results showed that it was effective in reducing the likelihood of accidents at uncontrolled crossings.

Proposed Solution

The proposed solution involves the use of a smart traffic management system that incorporates computer vision, machine learning, and IoT technologies to improve traffic management in the zone of unregulated pedestrian crossings in residential areas. The system consists of three main components:

1. **Pedestrian detection and classification module:** This module uses computer vision and machine learning techniques to detect and classify pedestrian movement at uncontrolled crossings. The module uses cameras mounted on poles near the crossings to capture real-time video footage of the area. The footage is analyzed using computer vision techniques such as object detection and tracking, and machine learning algorithms are used to classify the detected objects as pedestrians or non-pedestrians.

2. **Traffic control recommendation module:** This module receives input from the pedestrian detection and classification module and uses this information to provide real-time traffic control recommendations to drivers. The module is designed to take into account factors such as pedestrian movement, traffic volume, and road conditions to provide optimal traffic control recommendations to drivers. The recommendations can be displayed on electronic signs near the crossings or communicated to drivers through a mobile app.

3. **IoT sensor module:** This module consists of a network of IoT sensors that are used to detect and track pedestrian movement at uncontrolled crossings. The sensors can be embedded in the road surface or placed on poles near the crossings. The sensors detect pedestrian movement and communicate this information to the traffic control recommendation module, which uses this information to provide real-time traffic control recommendations to drivers.

The proposed solution has several potential benefits. Firstly, it could significantly reduce the likelihood of accidents at uncontrolled crossings by providing real-time traffic control recommendations to drivers. Secondly, it could improve traffic flow in residential areas by reducing the likelihood of traffic congestion at uncontrolled crossings. Thirdly, it could be cost-effective compared to traditional traffic control methods such as installing traffic lights or pedestrian crossing signals.

However, the proposed solution also has some limitations. Firstly, it may not be effective in areas with poor visibility or where pedestrian movement is not easily detectable, such as in areas with dense vegetation or low-light conditions. Secondly, it may be prone to false detections, leading

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to inaccurate traffic control recommendations. Lastly, the implementation of the system may require significant infrastructure investment, such as the installation of cameras, electronic signs, and IoT sensors.

Conclusion

Unregulated pedestrian crossings in residential areas pose a significant safety concern for both pedestrians and drivers. Traditional traffic control methods may not be effective in these areas, and new solutions are required to improve traffic management efficiency. This thesis proposes the use of a smart traffic management system that incorporates computer vision, machine learning, and IoT technologies to improve traffic management in the zone of unregulated pedestrian crossings in residential areas. The system consists of three main components: a pedestrian detection and classification module, a traffic control recommendation module, and an IoT sensor module. The proposed solution has several potential benefits, including improving safety, reducing traffic congestion, and being cost-effective compared to traditional traffic control methods. However, the solution also has some limitations, such as being ineffective in areas with poor visibility or where pedestrian movement is not easily detectable.

Future research can focus on addressing these limitations and improving the accuracy and reliability of the system. This could involve developing new computer vision and machine learning algorithms that are more robust to changes in lighting and weather conditions or investigating the use of alternative sensing technologies, such as LiDAR or radar, to improve pedestrian detection accuracy. Additionally, future research could investigate the impact of the proposed solution on traffic flow and safety in different residential areas and explore ways to integrate the system with existing traffic control infrastructure.

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